

The absorption and emission characteristics of some dithiocarbazate ligands and their Mo^{VI} complexes

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Abstract : The media effect on the absorption and emission properties and some photophysical studies of two free ligands, *S*-benzyl- β -*N*-(2-hydroxyphenyl) methylene dithiocarbazate (H_2L^1) and *S*-methyl- β -*N*-(2-hydroxyphenyl) methylene dithiocarbazate (H_2L^2) and their corresponding molybdenum Mo^{VI} complexes, MoO_2L^1 and $MoO_2L^2 \cdot H_2O$ are reported here. The steady state absorption and emission processes show that both free ligands and their metal complexes are found to depend on polarity of medium at room temperature. Here the emission of metal complexes is described to originate from the lowest excited states for ligand to metal charge transfer (LMCT). The spectral profile, shift in band maxima, quantum yield and fluorescence lifetime of metal complexes showed differences from those of free ligands. The Mo^{VI} complexes were found to show fluorescence quenching with respect to free ligands in those media.

Keywords : Dithiocarbazate, fluorescence quenching, LMCT, quantum yield, lifetime, absorption, emission.

Introduction

The study of dithiocarbazate ligands and its unique application as a donor ligand in complexation reactions with transitional metals draw considerable attention in recent years¹⁻⁵. These ligands are of immense importance in the applications also in other aspects, particularly as synthetic precursors⁶ and protecting groups⁷. These ligands are recently the subject of interest for showing non-linear optical (NLO) properties⁸, NLO parameters being calculated by using Z-scan technique. Recent study has reported the gas-phase pyrolysis of ketonic hydrazones from *S*-methyl dithiocarbazate along with some theoretical calculation⁴. Recent study has also reported two-photon absorption properties for Zn^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes of dithiocarbazate ligands along with their synthesis and characterization⁸.

The dithiocarbazate ligands having both hard (N, O) and soft (S) donor centers can readily react with transitional metals to form a stable complex. Among the transitional metals the coordination chemistry of higher valent molybdenum (Mo) ligated to mixed hard-soft nitrogen-sulfur donor ligands is a field of current interest be-

cause of their intrinsic relevance to the active sites of molybdoenzymes^{9,10}. The lower energy LUMO of these ligands are available for accepting electrons from the metal center. Also these ligands are important from the view point of enzyme modeling.

Our previous study¹¹ has established that Mo can form oxomolybdenum complexes with ligands *S*-benzyl- β -*N*-(2-hydroxyphenyl) methylene dithiocarbazate (H_2L^1) [Fig. 1(a)] and *S*-methyl- β -*N*-(2-hydroxyphenyl) methylene dithiocarbazate (H_2L^2) [Fig. 1(b)]. We have synthesized and characterized two Mo^{VI} complexes MoO_2L^1 and $MoO_2L^2 \cdot H_2O$ [Figs. 1(c) and 1(d)] from H_2L^1 and H_2L^2 respectively¹¹. In continuation of these studies we report here some photophysical aspects of them in different media having wide polarity difference with the help of absorption and emission spectroscopy at room temperature. The results are interpreted in terms of shift in absorption and emission band maxima and difference of quantum yield and lifetime values of metal complexes from those of free ligands. The fluorescence quenching of Mo^{VI} metal complexes with respect to free ligands in those media is also described here.

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Fig. 1. Structure of (a) MoO_2L^1 , (b) $\text{MoO}_2\text{L}^2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, (c) *S*-benzyl- β -*N*-(2-hydroxyphenyl) methylene dithiocarbamate (H_2L^1) and (d) *S*-methyl- β -*N*-(2-hydroxyphenyl) methylene dithiocarbamate (H_2L^2).

Materials and methods :

The chemicals used for preparative work were of reagent grade. The ligands H_2L^1 and H_2L^2 and their corresponding Mo^{VI} complexes MoO_2L^1 and $\text{MoO}_2\text{L}^2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ were prepared by our previous method¹¹. Spectroscopic grade dichloromethane (DCM) and dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) were used as solvents for the absorption and emission study. Absorption spectra were recorded in Hitachi U-3501 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Fluorescence emission spectra were taken using a Perkin-Elmer Luminescence spectrometer LS50B. Life time measurements were done using a Edinburgh Time correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) spectrometer ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 337 \text{ nm}$).

Results and discussion

Steady state absorption study :

We investigated steady state absorption of both free ligands and their Mo^{VI} metal complexes in several media at 298 K and observed their polarity dependence in UV-Vis region in those media, polarity being measured in terms of dielectric constant (D) of the medium. Here in this article we report steady state results for two solvents, dichloromethane (DCM, $D = 8.93$) and dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO, $D = 47.2$) so as to encompass the entire range of solvent polarity of our study to exhibit such polarity dependence. The absorption spectrum profiles of both H_2L^1 and H_2L^2 were identical in DCM and similar trend was noticed for their Mo complexes in the same solvent. For the ligands and metal complexes we observed same phenomenon in DMSO also. So here one representative spectrum is shown for H_2L^1 and its Mo complex in DCM, marked as (ax) [$\epsilon = 28000 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$]

Fig. 2. Representative absorption spectra for (ax), (bx), (ay) and (by), where (a) for H_2L^1 , (b) for MoO_2L^1 in (x) for DCM and (y) for DMSO, using 10^{-5} M in each case at 298 K.

Table 1. Absorption, emission maximum and quantum yield for H_2L^1 and H_2L^2 and their Mo^{VI} complexes in different media at 298 K

Comps.	Solvents	Absorption maximum (nm)	Emission maximum (nm)	Quantum yield
H_2L^1	DCM	349	387	0.006
MoO_2L^1		270	333	0.002
H_2L^2		346	390	0.008
$\text{MoO}_2\text{L}^2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$		306	336	0.003
H_2L^1	DMSO	376	515	0.025
MoO_2L^1		299	511	0.008
H_2L^2		355	504	0.027
$\text{MoO}_2\text{L}^2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$		320	510	0.006

and (bx) [$\epsilon = 15000 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$] respectively and in DMSO, marked as (ay) [$\epsilon = 18000 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$] and (by) [$\epsilon = 16000 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$] respectively in Fig. 2, ϵ being molar extinction coefficient for absorption maxima and corresponding absorption band maxima being shown in Table 1.

Comparing the pair of spectra : (1) (ax) and (bx) and (2) (ay) and (by) in Fig. 2 it is revealed that the absorption spectrum of metal complex contains broad bands and shows completely a different spectral profile from that of free ligand in those media. With the same spectrum profile change the absorption maxima for H_2L^2 and its metal complex are listed in Table 1. Here in both Mo complexes the lowest energy broad band in the visible region is LMCT transition due to the promotion of electron from the filled HOMO of the free ligand (primarily $\text{S}(\pi)$ character) to the empty LUMO of Mo($d\pi$) character and other LMCT bands are due to charge transfer transitions from N and O to Mo^{11,12}. With large increase in polarity of media LMCT bands are red shifted due to their charge transfer character^{11,12}. Figs. 2(ax) and (ay) showed that the absorption maximum of H_2L^1 for its chromophore¹³ is largely red shifted on increasing polarity. For the same polarity change this red shift is also observed for H_2L^2 , as seen from Table 1. Here large increase in polarity enhances the solvent interaction with both ground state and excited state of free ligands. Also the energy difference between ground state and excited state becomes smaller with increasing solvent polarity, causing red shift due to consequent decrease in transition energy¹⁴. From Table 1 it is seen that absorption maximum of H_2L^2 in DCM is blue shifted from that of H_2L^1 but this blue shift is greatly pronounced in DMSO because the electronic ground state of H_2L^2 is more stabilized in more polar solvent like DMSO¹⁴.

Steady state emission study :

Like steady state absorption we carried out emission experiments in DCM and DMSO at 298 K. In steady state emission both the metal complexes showed fluorescence quenching and shift of maxima from their free ligands in those media. Here also the emission spectrum profiles of both H_2L^1 and H_2L^2 were identical in DCM and similar trend was noticed for their Mo complexes in the same solvent. So we represent here emission spectrum for one free ligand, H_2L^2 and its metal complex in

Fig. 3. Representative emission spectra of (a) for H_2L^2 and (b) for $\text{MoO}_2\text{L}^2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in DCM, using in each case (1) 10^{-5} M at 298 K, (2) excitation band pass = 10 nm and emission band pass = 5 nm and (3) $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 306 \text{ nm}$.

Fig. 4. Emission spectra in DMSO using in each case (1) 10^{-5} M at 298 K, (2) excitation band pass = 10 nm and emission band pass = 5 nm and (3) $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 370 \text{ nm}$ for (a) and (b), 355 nm for (c) and 370 nm for (d), where (a) for H_2L^1 , (b) for MoO_2L^1 , (c) for H_2L^2 and (d) for $\text{MoO}_2\text{L}^2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

DCM in Figs. 3(a) and (b) respectively. Similar trend in emission spectrum profile was not observed in DMSO, so all the emission spectra for both free ligands and their Mo complexes in DMSO are depicted in Fig. 4, their emission maxima being provided in Table 1.

Here the emission for metal complexes can be described to originate from the lowest LMCT excited states in accord with the electron donating ability of free ligands^{3,5} and also with the fact that the emission maxima were independent of excitation wavelength in our desired spectrum range, such LMCT excited states for Mo^{VI} com-

plexes being also available in previous study¹⁵. The effect of polarity of medium on such states is very rare till date¹⁶. Here our LMCT excited states for metal complexes are further confirmed by the large red shift of the emission maxima of the metal complex in more polar solvent like DMSO due to more stabilization of excited states. From Figs. 3 and 4 and Table 1 it is very interesting to note that emission maximum of metal complex of H_2L^1 exhibited blue shift from that of its free ligand in both the media, but that of metal complex of H_2L^2 showed blue shift in DCM and red shift in DMSO with respect to free ligand. This difference may be attributed to less steric hindrance of a less bulky methyl group of second metal complex in a lower density medium (DMSO), thereby leading to more stable excited conformation of lower energy with emission in the red side¹⁷. Also with increase in polarity of medium the emission maxima of free ligands are red shifted due to markedly different excited state charge distribution of the solute than that in ground state, leading to a stronger interaction with highly polar solvent¹⁸. Figs. 3 and 4 showed fluorescence quenching of Mo^{VI} complexes from free ligands in both the media, this quenching phenomenon for such complex being described in detail in previous study¹⁹. The quantum yield (ϕ) values were also calculated by using standard equation²⁰ and ϕ for metal complexes were found to be less than that of free ligands in both the solvents and this can be attributed to the high probabilities of the deactivation of LMCT states. ϕ values for H_2L^1 and its metal complex were found to be 0.006 and 0.002 respectively in DCM, all ϕ values being listed in Table 1.

Time resolved emission study :

The nature of fluorescence quenching can be explained on the basis of lifetime (τ) measurement. We attempted to measure τ for both H_2L^1 and H_2L^2 and their Mo complexes both in DCM and DMSO. We got satisfactory τ value in DCM but not in DMSO. The emission intensity was not strong enough for reliable measurement of τ in DMSO. Again the τ of H_2L^1 and its Mo complex is very closer to that of H_2L^2 and its Mo complex in DCM with the identical decay profile. So one representative fluorescence intensity decay profile for H_2L^2 and its Mo complex in DCM is shown in Figs. 5(a) and (b) respectively, showing biexponential decay profile for both the cases.

Fig. 5. Count vs time (ns) decay profile (log-plot) of (a) H_2L^2 and (b) $MoO_2L^2.H_2O$ using 10^{-5} M concentration in DCM ($\lambda_{exc} = 337$ nm).

For different systems different reasons are suggested for the appearance of biexponential lifetime decay profile in previous study²¹⁻²³. In our case biexponential decay profile can be best explained on the basis of existence of two different tautomeric forms¹¹ in solution phase having different excited state lifetime. From Fig. 5 τ values for H_2L^2 and $MoO_2L^2.H_2O$ in DCM were found to be 3.0 ns and 4.02 ns respectively, this difference in lifetime values being consistent with the dynamic nature of quenching.

Conclusion :

Our study evinced that steady state absorption and emission of dithiocarbamate ligands and their Mo^{VI} complexes depend on the polarity of medium. The steady state emission for metal complexes is explained to arise from LMCT state. In emission study Mo complexes are found to quench from its free ligands, dynamic nature of quenching being observed. Our observations might be helpful in the application of dithiocarbamate ligands, potentially used for the anticancer and antibacterial activities.

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